

Preserving the orbiter: stabilization, disassembly, relocation and storage of an historic space shuttle mock-up

John Griswold – Questions and answer session

John Kemister: Did the murals get saved as well? On the side of the box?

John Griswold: They didn't. They got documented. But they got documented to a greater degree than they would have because – again this crossover between disciplines – being involved with historic preservation of structures as well, I was familiar with our HABS standards – our Historic American Building Survey standards for documentation. And so I knew a photographer who was able to come in and do that standard of photography for that space before it was demolished. But it was a sad thing to see those go.